

TEACHER COMPETENCE FOR ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT: PERCEPTION OF TEACHER EDUCATORS

Izuagba, A. C.ⁱ,

Afurobi, A. O.

PhD, Department of Curriculum and Instruction,
Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education,
Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

Abstract:

The intricate relationship between education and the sustainable development goals cannot be adequately discussed without a comprehensive understanding of the impact of the competences teachers bring to bear on their tasks which determine the extent of quality human resource development. This paper explored teacher educators' perception of their competences and how these competences shape effective teaching and learning for the achievement of sustainable development goals. This descriptive survey is guided by four research questions and three hypotheses. Population comprised all teacher educators in the colleges of education in south east geopolitical zone of Nigeria totaling 2,310. The simple random sampling with non-replacement balloting technique was employed to select a sample of 351 teacher educators. The instrument was an 18-item questionnaire and data generated were analysed using percentages and chi square. Results show that sex and years of experience did not have any significant difference in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs while academic qualification did. Based on these recommendations were made among which are the need to build the capacity of teacher educators on these new skills and the need to revise the teacher education curriculum to integrate these new skills required of learners in the knowledge driven market.

Keywords: teacher competence, sustainable development, educators' perception

ⁱ Correspondence: email winner4j@gmail.com, afurobiadaku@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

The role of education in development is not in doubt but for the development to be sustainable the content and process of the education programmes should be qualitative and inclusive. This implies that the education system must:

- provide learning that strengthens the capacities of learners to act progressively;
- provide learning environment that is healthy, safe, protective, respects the rights of learners and gender-sensitive with apt resources and facilities for teaching and learning;
- provide content and basic skills that are relevant, especially in the areas of literacy, numeracy and life skills, healthy living, nutrition, HIV/AIDS prevention and peace;
- provide relevant knowledge, skills and appropriate learning experiences that will help learners create for themselves and other places of safety, security and healthy interaction;
- be driven by knowledgeable and skilled teachers that use learner centred pedagogy in the teaching and learning process in order to effectively enact curriculum to reduce disparities among learners;
- be geared towards producing autonomous learners that are equipped with both hard and soft skills needed in the knowledge economy.

The Federal Government of Nigeria was conscious of this as it included most of the above indices of quality education in the goals of education in Nigeria as stipulated by FRN (2013), section (1), and sub-section (6) namely;

- Development of individual into a morally sound, patriotic and effective citizen;
- Total integration of the individual into immediate community, the Nigerian society and the world;
- Provision of equal access to qualitative educational opportunities for all citizens at all levels of education within and outside the formal school system;
- Inculcation of national consciousness, values and national unity and
- Development of appropriate skills, mental, physical and social abilities and competences to empower the individual to live and contribute positively to the society.

However, a critical analysis of the new demands posed by the SDGs revealed that learners require a new set of skills which invariably would demand different kinds of pedagogical approach from teachers and were not explicitly captured in the policy. Specifically, apart from the basic cognitive skills (include literacy and numeracy) which over the years have been emphasized in the education system; digital literacy and non-

cognitive skills have become essential skills for effective functioning in the world of work. The non-cognitive skills include: creativity, critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, emotional intelligence, inter-personal skills, and financial literacy, entrepreneurship skills etc (- generally referred to as soft skills).

As a matter of fact, a plethora of literature articulates clearly how teachers are the key factors that drive the education system which is the hub of manpower production for accelerating sustaining national development, (Ekpiken & Edet, 2014; USTESD, 2013; McKeown, 2013; Obanya, 2007; Darling-Hammond, 2006; Ukeje, 2002). Teachers possess power in their own capacity as the drivers of the education system to direct and groom the learners to become skilled, responsible and lifelong learners. In other words, even if access to education is increased, without the provision of competent teachers, people's capacity to think, reflect on issues, and reason critically to reach correct and wise decisions will not be enhanced and this will adversely affect the socio-economic development of the nation.

2. Importance of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in the Achievement of the Other 16 SDGs

The 17 SDGs were a follow up of the 8 MDGs in 2015. They were put forward to the General Assembly for approval in September 2015 by 184 Member States. The 17 SDGs have 169 targets that span from 2015-30 (UNESCO 2015). At the core of the 17 SDGs is goal number 4 "*Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote life-long learning opportunities for all*" which identified education not only as a part of the definition of sustainable development but also a means of achieving the SDGs. This is principally because quality education equips people with knowledge and competencies that increase their productivity thereby helping them to escape chronic poverty.

In providing inclusive and equitable quality education, lifelong learning which enhances social transformation process by involving everybody (without discrimination) in national development is facilitated thereby creating a just society. Inclusive and equitable quality education is critical for development as it makes it possible for people who hitherto were marginalized to enter the labour force and this will impact positively on family life and the environment through the use of efficient energy sources, healthy consumption habits and healthy family life style. Inclusive and equitable quality education is the key tool for economic, social, technological and ethical reorientation which reduces the incidence of crime, strife, threats to personal or family security that arise due to discontentment emanating from exclusion and inequality.

Consequently, the 184 Member States of the UNESCO affirm that achieving the 169 targets of the SDGs that will lay the foundation of a peaceful world is possible only through the provision of inclusive, equitable quality education that is compulsory and free from early child care education (ECCE) through, primary education, secondary education, vocational and higher education. Hitherto, emphasis was on compulsory free primary education, but the demands of the SDGs and the 2030 agenda recognise that primary education is far from enough in today's world, hence the inclusion of ECCE, secondary, and tertiary education as well as vocational and technical education- to ensure everyone is equipped for productivity and for the conservation of the biodiversity.

A closer examination of the 17 SDGs shows that their goals are intertwined. For instance, SDG₄ also made explicit the type of education that will ensure that the 169 targets of the 17 SDGs are achieved by using the key phrase: 'inclusive, equitable and qualitative education'. These three adjectives give pointer to the content and process dimensions of the education programme/system that can guarantee the promotion of life-long learning and acquisition of relevant skills for the sustainable development of nations and the entire world.

In other words, if SDG₄ is achieved by 2030, everybody will be functionally literate (based on the 21st century conception of literacy) and skilled and this will promote gender equality, eliminate all forms of inequality. Consequently, people will realize the need to conserve energy and sustain the natural environment, as well as take urgent action to combat climate change. In addition, poverty will be greatly minimized because of access to quality education and skills acquired through vocational and technical education that is qualitative. The results would be a productive workforce that will promote sustainable economic growth and safety, which will lead to the development of resilient infrastructure.

The catch phrase is 'inclusive, equitable and qualitative' education, which implies that the school programmes and activities must be such that accepts and respects the right of every child to learn and ensures that they learn in the ways they want to learn without discrimination. Also all variables that breed injustice and discriminations arising from learners' socio-economic background, race, gender, HIV/AIDs status, etc are eliminated. Most important is that teachers that drive the system will be adequately tooled and supported to teach effectively.

At the core of the implementation of the SDGs is the teacher. Obviously, it is not any caliber of a teacher, as teachers whose orientation are highly skewed towards teaching children to pass examinations and those who utilize mainly the teacher centred methods cannot positively impact either on SDG₄ nor on the other 16 SDGs.

Thus, the teacher becomes a major factor in the strategies for achieving the targets of the SDGs.

In the same vein, a teacher education curriculum that emphasizes only the development of cognitive competences will definitely be inadequate, as a more critical, expansive orientation to knowledge and technological-pedagogical-content-knowledge is required for equitable, quality education to be achieved. The implication is that teacher education programmes must equip teacher trainees with these soft skills as well as technological- pedagogical-content knowledge that will enable them effectively equip learners for sustainable development.

Unfortunately, UNESCO (2014) found that around 250 million children are not learning basic skills, even though half of them have spent at least four years in school. Affirming this deficiency in teachers, Rose & Alcott (2015); ESSPIN (2010); Okebukola, (2005) said teachers are unable to perform numeracy and literacy tasks for which they are meant to be preparing their pupils. To fill this gap, they called for appropriate training that incorporates practical classroom experience which will enable teachers support children to learn the basic skills and to progress at the right pace. It thus implies that if teachers in public schools lack the proficiency to do their work, government cannot deliver inclusive, equitable quality education unless it improves on the capacity of teachers in all the levels of the education system. If we consider the fact that teachers tend to teach as they were taught, the need to institutionalize in-service training through the establishment of learning communities in schools where teachers support each other using peer collaboration rather than one-stop seminars and conferences becomes an imperative.

In the same vein, the use of collaborative strategies and assessment for learning rather than assessment of learning may become part of the pedagogies that can empower student- teachers to become effective and efficient teachers (USTESD Network, 2013; McKeown, 2013). To further help teachers achieve the SDGs, there may be need to help teachers become flexible in teaching and autonomous to be able to exercise judgment in adopting ideas that suit their personal style (McKeown, 2013).

3. Teacher Competences Required for the Achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Competences refer to knowledge, abilities, skills, aptitude, values, attitudes and behaviour patterns teachers are expected to deploy in carrying out their daily teaching and other related tasks in order to adequately equip learners to contribute and function effectively in their society. The General Directorate of Education, Vocational Training

and Learning Innovation (2011, p. 8) defined competency as *'the conscious use of one's own knowledge, abilities, skills, talents, values, attitudes and behaviour patterns, in order to resolve issues and problems, overcome challenges, fulfilling one's duties and achieving the aims proposed'*. These competences include cognitive knowledge (which refers to their tacit knowledge and use of theories, concepts), affective disposition (which refers to their attributes, soft skills and organizational skills) and psychomotor competences (their technical and manipulative skills). Specifically, teachers' competences refer to the teacher's ability to utilise their knowledge, abilities, soft skills, attitudes and behaviour patterns in order to effectively equip learners for life.

To really comprehend the different dimensions of teacher competences the expected teacher competences by these institutions is used as reference. They are: the Advisory Committee on Teacher Education and Qualifications, (2003, p. 24-41) which listed fifteen teacher competences while General Directorate of Education, Vocational Training and Learning Innovation (2011, p. 39-48) identified ten and the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria, (2012 p 24-51) identified teachers' competences under four main themes and 36 sub-themes. These competences when put together give a holistic picture of an effective teacher practice and these are summarized thus:

1. Sound knowledge of the core subject: This competency is crucial for effective teaching, as he must have sound knowledge of the substantive content of the subject he/she teaches as well as knowledge of how to present it to students in such a way that both the formal content and the informal content blend into a seamless whole. As a matter of fact, some research studies found a strong correlation between teachers' subject knowledge and student achievement (ESSPIN, 2010; Okebukola, 2005; Ukeje, 2002; Ipaye, 2000), though, some other studies contradicts this and demand sound pedagogic content knowledge (PCK) (Darling-Hammond, 2006; Shulman, 1986) and sound technological pedagogic content knowledge (TPACK) (Koehler, Mishra, Kereluik, Shin, & Graham, 2014; Guerrero, 2010). Apart from the above, the teacher must also have knowledge of the curriculum of the level of education he/she teaches to be able to select and use apt resources (-pictures, technology, analogies) to facilitate interaction and deep thinking among learners (Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria, 2012).
2. The ability to successfully align technologies with content and pedagogy in order to make the lesson comprehensible to learners is another competency expected of teachers for the achievement of sustainable national development. Specifically, this competency requires that teachers use their knowledge and understandings of technology, pedagogy, and content to make learning meaningful and real to learners in spite of differences in interest, needs and learning styles. For Guerrero

(2010) this refers to the teachers' ability to adjust the use of technology to serve the varied needs of diverse learners in the class. Utilizing this competency implies that teachers adequately prepare the learners for the world of work especially for the 21st century labour market that is knowledge driven.

3. Aptly balancing direct instruction with the learner centred methods is a key competency. This is tied to the teachers' pedagogic competence (PK) and Pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) which requires teachers to apply varied teaching methods to facilitate learner engagement. This is an important competency a teacher must have if he must carry every learner along. To really make the lesson comprehensible to learners, teachers must know what make a subject difficult or easy to learn, as well as common misconceptions the students bring with them to the lesson and must address these first before effective learning can take place (Shulman, 1986).
4. Ability to apply their knowledge of child and adolescent development in lesson preparation, implementation and evaluation is another competence necessary in designing good lesson plans that will be suitable for the developmental stages of the learners; as well as for the diversity that exists among the learners. Integrating developmentally appropriate practices into classroom instruction means meeting the students at the developmental stages they are currently thereby enabling them to reach the goals that are set for them. Failure to take these into considerations in lesson planning, implementation and evaluation means that the objectives of the lessons will not be achieved.
5. Another competency expected is the apt use of a range of assessment strategies (rubric, e-portfolios, formative assessment, summative, peer assessment, observation etc). The knowledge and the ability to use a variety of assessment tools provide the teachers with different sources of evidence which help him to accurately interpret what each child actually knows and will be able to do at each point in time.
6. Commitment to continuing professional development is career-long obligation for practicing teachers, to enable them keep abreast with current knowledge and skills so that they can effectively prepare learners not only for the present, but also for the ever-changing future. It is based on the importance of continual professional development in enhancing teachers' competences for meeting the goals of education that UNESCO (2015) and Bangs (2016) call for more support for teachers in the areas of capacity building especially, in view of the growing demand for new sets of skills in the knowledge-driven labour market.

7. A good communicative and inter-personal skill is another competency. This encompasses teachers' personality traits to include ability to effectively use the soft skills which include communicative skills, creative and critical thinking skills, emotional intelligence, good sense of humour, a sense of fairness, flexibility, empathy, patience, enthusiasm etc in performing their tasks. Effective use of soft skills help teachers manage classroom dynamics, manage interpersonal relationships, diversity in the classroom, support learners and colleagues in order to build a learning community that will facilitate national development, (adapted from AACTE and Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21) (2010, p. 11-12).

4. Statement of the Research Problem

Stakeholders and employers of labour in the education sector have shown displeasure at the quality of products of the system and some attributed it to poor funding, low motivation of teachers among others. However, results from research on teacher education and teacher quality suggest that there is mismatch between the actual and the expected competences (Adeosun, 2012; Anikweze, 2012; Abanikanda, 2011; ESSPIN, 2010; Obanya, 2007). The findings of Adeosun (2012); Delrosario, & Adgoke (2011) highlight the general weakness of education graduates. It is on this basis that Ekpiken and Edet (2014) argues that teachers are not adequately equipped with the expected competences because government policies and programmes have not been adequately matched with the implementation process. Unfortunately, none of the studies investigated whether teacher educators are aware of the competences expected of their products for effective teaching in the 21st century.

Nwokeocha (2013) added that a majority of teachers are not aware of the competences expected of them as paucity of funds has made it difficult for the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria to implement its policies that would have created quality awareness in teachers. The question is: Since teacher educators produce teachers that drive the education system, what is their perception of these competences expected of teachers they produce?

4.1. Research Objectives

It is on the light of the above that the researchers set out to determine teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Find out whether sex influences teacher educators perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.
2. Find out whether years of experience influences teacher educators perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.
3. Determine if educational qualification influences teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.

4.2. Research Questions

1. What is teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs?
2. To what extent does sex influence teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs?
3. To what extent do years of experience influence teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs?
4. To what extent does educational qualification influence teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs?

4.3. Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between male and female teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.
2. There is no significant difference in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on years of experience.
3. There is no significant difference in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on educational qualification.

5. Methodology

This study was a descriptive survey designed to determine teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs. The population comprises all teacher educators in south east geopolitical zone totaling 2,310. The simple random sampling with non-replacement balloting techniques was employed. Sample size was determined using Watson (2001) in which consideration were made on the estimate of variability of the population, estimated response rate and

confidence level of 95% which is standard for social science researches. Watson (2001) then yielded 351 which was divided between the colleges of education in south east geopolitical zone thus; 87, 88, 88, and 88.

The instrument was an 18-item questionnaire developed by researchers in which options provided were Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The questionnaire was divided into two sections A and B. Section A dealt with the respondent's personal data while section B dealt with teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs. Instrument was validated by two experts in educational measurement and evaluation. Their inputs were effected in the final draft. The test retest method was used to test for the reliability of the instrument. Data generated were subjected to Person's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient which yielded an index of 0.78. The instrument was therefore judged to be reliable.

Five research assistants were used for the administration of instrument on a face to face basis. All instrument administered were returned but three were not properly filled, therefore were discarded, leaving 348 for data analysis. Data generated from survey instrument were analysed using simple percentages and chi-square test of independence.

6. Results and Findings

Research Question 1: What is the nature of teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs?

In order to answer the research question, data collected were analysed using simple percentage as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Percentage responses on the nature of teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs

	Perception		<u>Total</u>
	Positive	Negative	
Responses	110	238	348
Percentages	31.6%	68.4%	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

The above table shows that a majority of teacher educators had a negative perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs. A total of 238 or 68.4% of respondents had a negative perception while 110 or 31.6% a positive.

Research Question 2: To what extent does sex influence teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs?

In order to answer the research question, data collected were analysed using simple percentage as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Percentage responses of teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on sex

Sex	Perception					
	Positive		Negative		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
Male	57	(16.4)	115	(33)	172	(49.4)
Female	53	(15.2)	123	(35.4)	176	(50.6)
Total	110	(31.6)	238	(68.4)	348	(100)

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

The above table shows that 57 or 16.4% of male respondents showed a positive perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs while 115 or 33% a negative. 53 or 15.2% of female respondents showed a positive perception while 123 or 35.4% had a negative perception. The conclusion is that sex is not a factor in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.

Research Question 3: To what extent do years of experience influence teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs?

In order to answer the research question, data collected were analysed using simple percentage as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Percentage responses on teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on years of experience

Years of Experience	Perception					
	Positive		Negative		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
5-10	59	(16.9)	130	(37.3)	189	(54.3)
11+	51	(14.7)	108	(31.1)	151	(45.7)
Total	110	(31.6)	238	(68.4)	348	(100)

Source: Field Survey, 2017

The above table shows that 59 or 16.9% of respondents of 5-10 years of experience showed a positive perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs while 130 or 37.3% a negative perception. 51 or 14.7% of respondents of 11+ years of experience showed positive perception while 108 or 31.1% a negative perception. The conclusion is that years of experience is not a factor of teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.

Research Question 4: To what extent does academic qualification influence teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs?

To answer the research question, data collected were analysed using simple percentage as shown in Table 4

Table 4: Percentage responses of influence of academic qualification on teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs

Academic Qualification	Positive		Perception Negative		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
MEd/MSc	46	(13.2)	142	(40.8)	188	(54)
PhD	64	(18.4)	96	(27.6)	160	(46)
Total	110	(31.6)	230	(68.4)	348	(100)

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

The above table shows that 46 or 13.2% of teacher educators with Med/MSc showed positive perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs while 142 or 40.8% negative perception. 64 or 18.4% of respondents with PhD showed a positive perception while 96 or 27.6% negative perception. The conclusion is that academic qualification is not a factor in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.

6.1 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.

To test this null hypothesis, data collected were analysed using chi-square

Table 5: Chi Square test of male and female teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs

Sex	Perception			X ² cal	X ² _{0.05}	df	Result
	Positive	Negative	Total				
Male	57	115	172	0.36	3.84	1	Not Significant
Female	53	123	176				
Total	110	238	348				

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Since $X^2_{cal} = 0.36$ is less than $X^2_{0.05} = 3.84$ at degree of freedom 1, we accept null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference between male and female teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on years of experience.

To test the null hypothesis, data collected were analysed using chi-square for table 6

Table 6: Chi-Square test of teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on years of experiences

Years of Experience	Perception			X ² cal	X ² _{0.05}	Df	Result
	Positive	Negative	Total				
5-10	59	130	189	0.02	3.84	1	Not Significant
11+	51	108	159				
Total	119	238	348				

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Since $X^2_{cal} = 0.02$ is less than $X^2_{0.05} = 3.84$ at degree of freedom 1, we accept null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on years of experience.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on academic qualification.

To test this null hypothesis, data collected were analysed using chi-square

Table 7: Chi Sq. test of teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on academic qualification

Academic Qualification	Perception		Total	X ² cal	X ² _{0.05}	df	Result
	Positive	Negative					
Med/MSc	46	142	188	9.64	3.84	1	Significant
PhD	64	96	160				
Total	110	238	348				

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Since $X^2_{cal} = 9.64$ is greater than $X^2_{0.05} = 3.84$ at degree of freedom 1, we reject null hypothesis and conclude that there is significant difference in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on educational qualification.

7. Discussion

The study sought to determine teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs using 348 lecturers from colleges of education in the five states that make up South East Geopolitical Zone. Data analyzed in table 1 in response to the first research question showed that teacher educators had a negative perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs. A great majority of respondents (238 or 68.4%) showed negative perception. This supports Adeosun (2012), Anikweze (2012), Abanikanda (2011), ESSPIN (2010) and Obanya (2007) who identified mismatch between the actual and the expected competences in teachers produced and Adeosun (2012) and Durosaro, & Adgoke (2011) who highlighted the general weakness of education graduates. In other words, if teacher educators have a positive perception of these competences they would work towards infusing them in the content and process of their lessons.

Results in tables 2 and 5 show that sex is not a factor in in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs. This is because a majority of the respondents showed negative perception. 123 or 35.4% of female respondents in table 2 showed negative perception and 115 or 33% of male respondents also had negative perception. The Chi-Square test (table 5) for this also confirmed the result in table 2 with $X^2_{cal} = 0.36$ being less than $X^2_{cal} = 3.84$ at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom 1. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted and upheld. The conclusion reached is that sex is not determining factor of in teacher

educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs.

Results in tables 3 and 6 also shows that years of experience is not a determining factor of in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs. A great percentage of the respondents of 5-10 years of service (37.3%) showed negative perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs. Meanwhile, another great percentage of (31.1) 11+ years of service also showed negative perception. The chi-square test in table 6 further confirmed this result with $X^2_{cal} = 0.02$ which is less than $X^2_{0.05} = 3.84$ at degree of freedom 1, based on this the null hypothesis was accepted and upheld. The conclusion is that there is no significant difference in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs based on years of experience.

Result in tables 4 and 7 show some interesting development. Whereas table 4 shows that academic qualification is not a factor in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs, the data analysed in table 7 show the contrary when the same data was subjected to chi square test. $X^2_{cal} = 9.64$ was found to be greater than the tabulated chi square 3.84 at degree of freedom 1. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected and the alternative hypothesis upheld leading to the conclusion that there is significant difference in teacher educators' perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs. This means that academic qualification is a determining factor of teacher educators' perception.

8. Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from this study is that teacher educators' have negative perception of the competences expected of teachers for the achievement of the SDGs. In addition, academic qualification was found to influence teacher educators' perception while years of experience and sex did not influence their perception.

9. Recommendation

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

1. The curriculum of teacher education should be revised with a view to integrate these new skills and emergent innovative pedagogies.

2. The capacity of teacher educators should be developed to equip them with these new skills and related innovative pedagogies to enable them produce quality teachers for the global market.
3. Continual professional development should be mandatory for all teacher educators to keep them abreast with current trends in teaching and learning
4. The new skills should be integrated into the instrument used for assessing teacher educators for promotion to ensure compliance.

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